

AN IN-DEPTH STUDY ON PERCEPTION OF EMPLOYEES ON VALUE SYSTEMS OF BHARATH SANCHAR NIGAM LIMITED

(With special reference to AP and Telangana)

Dr. EluriVenuMadhavi^{#1}, Dr. M.Srinivasa Sessa Sai^{*2}

^{#1}Associate Professor, Vignan's Nirula Institute of Technology and Sciences for Women, Guntur,
AP, India

^{#2}Professor, KKR & KSR Institute of Technology and Sciences, Guntur, AP, India

#1elurivenumadhavi@gmail.com, #2mssai@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Values guide not only individuals but organizations as well. It is so especially when organizations are running their operations in public utilities. Mining is one such industry where work is carried on in utmost unsafe conditions. Workers are not only exposed to hazardous mining processes but also susceptible to various occupational diseases. Hence, a good corporate culture is not only desirable but even inevitable for the smooth functioning of the organizations. The present article is a lucid attempt to understand and analyze the perception of employees on the value system adopted by a Giant in mining industry called Bharath Sanchar Nigam Limited. This article throws light on the perception of employees of BSNL on various aspects of value systems followed by the company. It also studies and analyzes the differences between the opinions of executives and non-executives on the value systems.

Keywords: Organizational Values, Culture, BSNL, welfare, Promptitude, welfare facilities, retirement benefits, executives, non-executives.

INTRODUCTION:

Bharat Sanchar Nigam Ltd. was incorporated on 15th september 2000. It entered the business of providing of telecom services and network management from the erstwhile Central Government Departments of Telecom Services (DTS) and Telecom Operations (DTO), with effect from 1st October'2000 on going concern basis. It is one of the biggest & principal public sector units providing comprehensive range of telecom services in India.

BSNL has installed Quality Telecom Network in the country & now focusing on improving it, expanding the network, introducing new telecom services with ICT applications in villages & winning customer's confidence. For the sustained growth of any organization, especially the one which is in public sector, creating and sustaining a positive and proactive organizational culture is very important. Organizational culture is to some extent represented by the value systems adopted by it. Values are the beliefs of people as to what is fundamentally good and what is bad. Values direct the behavior of individuals and organizations. Value systems followed by organizations give distinct identity to not only the employees who are part of it but they are also appreciated by the society in which it is part of.

According to Rokeach¹, values are "abstract ideas, positive or negative, not tied to any specific object or situation, and represent a person's beliefs about modes of conduct and ideal terminal modes". Organizational values are defined as deep rooted, enduring, fundamental beliefs among organizational members about different aspects of organizational life. Values play a central role within the lives of citizenry. Much of human behavior is predicated on the values they hold both individually and collectively. They supply a typical or act as a benchmark for fundamental norms of human process against which behavior is guided and evaluated. For a public sector Giant like BSNL, creating and sustaining a robust organizational culture is not only desirable but also imperative. However, in the last few years, BSNL has seen lots of ups and downs in its business due

to acute competition from business rivals. This will obviously have an impact on the morale of its employees. The financial position of BSNL has also deteriorated due to the challenging circumstances under which it is operating. Hence, sustaining the morale of employees is need of the day. With this backdrop, the researcher felt it appropriate to study the perception of employees on the value system of BSNL.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Srivastava (2009)² made an attempt to investigate the relationship between organizational structure, communication, nature of task and organizational effectiveness. The findings indicated that openness in communication was positively related to effectiveness. Two dimensions of structure such as formalization and participation were positively related while centralization was negatively related to organizational effectiveness. Soumendu Biswas (2009)³ felt that organizational culture and transformational leadership were found to have important bearing on human resource development and the performance of individual employees. Prabhjot Kaur Mahal (2009)⁴ examined the influence of organizational culture and climate on the motivation level of 100 adult employees in Ranbaxy. The study found that the factors of organizational culture and climate have a positive fall-out on the motivation level of employees. Elangovan and Jayashree (2013)⁵ made an attempt to investigate the organizational culture that exist in Salem steel plant. The investigation revealed that factors such as knowledge about the organizational policy, work environment, values and beliefs, attitude towards work, work involvement and inter personal relationships have the capacity in building organizational culture. Owino O. Joseph & Kieran Francis (2015)⁶ assessed the influence of organizational culture and market orientation on the performance microfinance institutions. They concluded that the influence of organizational culture and market orientation on the performance is more plausible for mature industries regarded as diverse in terms of customer needs. Nidhin S and Komal Chopra (2015)⁷ found that productivity is largely dependent on employee's involvement, teamwork, peer communication, role clarity, physical work conditions, infrastructure, resources and compensation. Petia Zenkova and Anna Gajda (2017)⁸ threw light on the mergers & acquisitions process initiated by a German based multinational company. The study results show that there is a great need to develop new culture after the M& A process is completed. Aparna Vajpayee (2017)⁹ observed that foreign MNCs have rich organizational culture than Indian MNCs and this is evident from their approach towards employees. The author felt that Foreign MNCs have more trust on their employees and hence they give more individual freedom to employees by which they can exercise their creative and innovative abilities. VasudhaDhingra, Kamlesh Gakhar(2014)¹⁰ studied and compared the employee development practices of BSNL and MSNL and concluded that employee developmental programs should be carried on on a continuous basis.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: The present study aims at identifying and analyzing the opinions of employees of Bharath Sanchar Nigam Limited on various aspects of value systems adopted by the management of BSNL. It also aims at understanding whether there exists any difference between the perception of executives and non-executives with respect to the value systems followed by the management of BSNL.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

H0: There is no significant difference between the opinions of executives and non- executives about the organizational culture that prevails in BSNL.

H1: There is significant difference between the opinions of executives and non- executives about the organizational culture that prevails in BSNL

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study makes use of both primary and secondary data. Secondary data for the study has

been collected from the official website of BSNL and primary data has been collected through Opinion survey conducted for a selected number of sample respondents.

SELECTION OF SAMPLE ORGANIZATION AND RESPONDENTS

With a view to study and analyze the Organizational Culture in BSNL, a questionnaire was prepared and served to the employees of BSNL. At present, there are 30,887 executives and 38937 non-executives working for BSNL¹². Hence, the study is confined executives and non-executives working in AP and Telangana states. Simple random sampling technique has been employed in the present study. For the purpose of understanding the opinion of respondents, 62 executives and 582non-executives were chosen as sample respondents.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT: To take up the present study a questionnaire with 20 statements pertaining to different aspects of value systems adopted by BSNL is prepared and administered.

STATISTICAL TOOLS USED: To test the hypothesis, Chi-square test , ANOVA and t-test have also been used to analyze the data.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

Table -1
BSNL is open and just in its dealings with stakeholders

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Executives	Non-executives	Total
1	V Strongly agree	(29.03%) 18	(35.91%) 209	(35.25%) 227
2	V Agree	(61.29%) 38	(49.31%) 287	(50.47%) 325
3	V Undecided	(9.68%) 6	(8.25%) 48	(8.38%) 54
4	V Disagree	-	(6.53%) 38	(5.90%) 38
5	V Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 62	(100%) 582	(100%) 644
Weighted average mean score		4.19	4.15	4.15
Chi square test Values		Calculated value: 6.53	Table value: 7.815	
Anova test values		C value: 4.412	T value: 5.987	
T test values		C value: (- 2.1)	T value: 2.446	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

The above table indicates that more than 50 % of the respondents agree that the management of BSNL is open and just in its dealings with all its stakeholders. Only 6% of the respondents expressed a different opinion. When the Chi Square test is carried on, results showed that the calculated value is at 6.53 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 7.815. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results validate the above observation. It shows that BSNL is open and just in its dealings with stakeholders.

Table-2
The company provides welfare amenities to the contentment of employees

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Executives	Non-executives	Total
1	Strongly agree	(56.45%) 35	(43.13%) 251	(44.41%) 286
2	Agree	(32.26%) 20	(39.86%) 232	(39.13%) 252
3	Undecided	(8.06%) 5	(9.62%) 56	(9.47%) 61
4	Disagree	(3.22%) 2	(7.39%) 43	(6.98%) 45
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 62	(100%) 582	(100%) 644
Weighted average mean score		4.42	4.19	4.21
Chi square values		Calculated value: 4.601	Table value: 7.815	
Anova test values		C value: 5.3619	T value: 5.987	
T test values		C value: (-2.3155)	T value: 2.446	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

The above table reveals that 44% of the respondents strongly agreed that the management of BSNL is providing welfare amenities to the contentment of employees whereas only a few contradicted with them. When the Chi Square test is carried on, results showed that the calculated value is at 4.601 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 7.815. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results validate the above observation.

Table-3 The company pays bonus to all the employees irrespective of position

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Executives	Non-executives	Total
1	Strongly agree	(43.55%) 27	(45.02%) 262	(44.88%) 289
2	Agree	(56.45%) 35	(47.25%) 275	(48.14%) 310
3	Undecided	-	(7.73%) 45	(6.98%) 45
4	Disagree	-	-	-
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 62	(100%) 582	(100%) 644
Weighted average mean score		4.44	4.37	4.38
Chi square test values		Calculated value: 5.806	Table value: 5.991	
Anova test values		C value: 5.2928	T value: 7.7086	
T test values		C value: (- 2.3)	T value: 2.776	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

The above table reveals that 45% of the respondents strongly agreed that the management of BSNL is paying bonus to all the employees irrespective of their position whereas only a few contradicted with them. When the Chi Square test is carried on, results showed that the calculated value is at 5.806 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 5.991. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results validate the above observation.

Table-4 The company is community welfare oriented

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Executives	Non-executives	Total
1	Strongly agree	(54.84%) 34	(41.92%) 244	(43.17%) 278

2	Agree	(45.16%) 28	(50.86%) 296	(50.31%) 324
3	Undecided	-	(5.67%) 33	(5.12%) 33
4	Disagree	-	(1.55%) 9	(1.40%) 9
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 62	(100%) 582	(100%) 644
Weighted average mean score		4.55	4.33	4.35
Chi square test values		Calculated value: 7.001	Table value: 7.815	
Anova test values		C value: 3.1383	T value: 5.987	
T test values		C value: (-) 1.7715	T value: 2.446	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

Table-4 shows that more than half of the respondents agreed that their management is community welfare oriented whereas only a negligible portion of the respondents disagreed with the statement. The above table reveals that 44% of the respondents strongly agreed that the management of BSNL is providing welfare amenities to the contentment of employees whereas only a few contradicted with them. When the Chi Square test is carried on, results showed that the calculated value is at 7.001 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 7.815. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results validate the above observation.

Table-5

The company is employee safety oriented

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Executives	Non-executives	Total
1	Strongly agree	(41.94%) 26	(44.16%) 257	(43.94%) 283
2	Agree	(58.06%) 36	(51.72%) 301	(52.33%) 337
3	Undecided	-	(4.12%) 24	(3.73%) 24
4	Disagree	-	-	-
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 62	(100%) 582	(100%) 644

Weighted average mean score	4.42	4.40	4.40
Chi square test values	Calculated value: 3.051	Table value: 5.991	
Anova test values	C value: 4.0051	T value: 7.7086	
T test values	C value: (-) 2.001	T value: 2.776	

Source: primary data

When asked about the safety orientation of the employees, most of the respondents felt that BSNL gives utmost preference employees safety. The following chart depicts the opinion of respondents on the same. The above table reveals that 44% of the respondents strongly agreed that the management of BSNL is providing welfare amenities to the contentment of employees whereas only a few contradicted with them. When the Chi Square test is carried on, results showed that the calculated value is at 3.051 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 5.991. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results validate the above observation.

CONCLUSION:

This study is mainly carried out to know the value systems followed by the management of BSNL and also to identify whether there is a difference in the perception of executives and non-executives about the value systems present in BSNL and it is found that there is no difference between the perception of executives and non-executives is the same. The welfare wing implements all the provisions relating to employee welfare such as processing the cases of dependents for employment besides undertaking welfare related programs such as “Special Welfare Amenities Programs” in workmen colonies. The company pays three types of bonus to employees such as attendance bonus, performance linked bonus and profit bonus.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Research is unending and hence there is a lot of scope to study many other areas of Organizational Behaviour in other public utility organizations.

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